

16 KBPS APC WITH HYBRID QUANTIZATION

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ABSTRACT

This paper presents the results of a two year effort to develop an adaptive predictive coder for transmission of high quality speech over 16 Kbps channels with up to a 5% bit error rate. To maximize intelligibility and maintain bandwidth compatibility with existing speech compression systems, an 8 KHz A-D sampling rate constraint was imposed.

Our algorithm, called APC-HQ for "hybrid quantization," concentrates on improving the residual coding and uses both segmental quantization and center clipping quantization in a perceptually optimum manner. The result is an algorithm running in real time on an AP-120B [4] which yields high quality under the input bandwidth and noisy channel constraints, and whose speech quality exceeds that attainable with either technique alone.

INTRODUCTION

For some time we have been investigating ways to further take advantage of APC residual characteristics over and above our segmental quantizer APCSQ [2] which operates at 9.6 Kbps. The residual, because it absorbs about three quarters of the transmission rate, seemed the place for significant gains to be made.

In 1981, the Digital Voice Processor Consortium of the U. S. Department of Defense announced that in late 1983 they would conduct tests of various 16 Kbps speech compression systems. These tests would include measurements of intelligibility and quality based on diagnostic rhyme tests and diagnostic acceptability measure tests for many different test conditions. Test conditions were to include random and burst errors at rates up to five percent, input speech corrupted by various types of acoustic noise, and speech tandemed with other coders such as LPC-10 and 16 Kbps CVSD. Due to the nature of the testing, the speech would have to be processed in real-time.

This 16 Kbps rate became the target of our investigations into improving adaptive predictive coding. We chose an 8 KHz sampling rate based on our belief that the tandem with the LPC-10 coder would suffer if a bandwidth significantly less than four KHz was used. A wider bandwidth would not appreciably increase intelligibility but would increase the quantization noise of the coder.

Recent research on APC has been published by Viswanathan et al of BBN [3] and by Atal of Bell Labs [1]. However the BBN algorithm uses two bits per residual sample and therefore is not applicable to a 16 Kbps APC with an 8 KHz sampling rate. The run length coding described by Atal for his center clipping residual encoding technique would suffer excessively in channel errors.

The algorithm we developed for testing, called APC-HQ for "hybrid quantization," concentrates on the residual coding problem and uses both segmental quantization and center clipping to achieve better performance than can be achieved by either technique alone. The result is an algorithm running in real time on an AP-120B [4] which yields high quality and intelligibility.

The heart of the system, diagrammed in Figure 1, is the switched residual quantizers. In addition, the APC-HQ system contains a second order pitch whitening filter whose parameters are updated at twice the frame rate of 38 frames per second. Following the pitch whitening filter is a ninth order spectral whitening filter. A moderate amount of pre- and deemphasis is used. This prewhitening has the effect of reducing spectral parameter dynamic range and the number of unstable frames, and the deemphasis provides a degree of low pass noise shaping.

We will first discuss our motivation for using both a center clipping and a segmental quantizer, and will describe its algorithmic implementation. This is followed by a description of the switched use of the segment quantizer and its implementation. Next, innovations in the pitch whitening area will be described followed by a discussion of coding and error protection.

RESIDUAL ENCODING

We knew from observations of residual signals that during voiced sounds a large amount of the residual energy is concentrated in short duration spikes spaced pitch intervals apart. The peakedness of the residual is due mainly to the spectral whitening filter whose effect, in addition to whitening the residual spectrum, is to increase the peakedness of the time domain waveform.

Attempts to use pitch information to code the positions of these peaks or spikes proved algorithmically complex and time intensive. In addition, pitch synchronous coding in the area of the largest spikes at the beginning of each epoch left uncoded secondary spikes occurring further into the pitch epoch. These facts caused us to look favorably on the center clipping and run length coding ideas of Atal which could code these spikes wherever they occurred.

However, during sounds such as unvoiced consonants, where little spiking occurs, the residual energy is fairly evenly spread over all the residual samples, and a fixed number of bits per sample and segmental quantization still proved superior. It was thus decided to retain the best of both techniques by running both quantizers and letting the frame S/R (signal to residual energy ratio) determine which to transmit.

QUANTIZATION AND ENCODING OF
THE CENTER CLIPPED PREDICTION RESIDUAL

One of the coding techniques discussed by Atal [1] to handle a prediction residual with a large number of zeroes was a run length code of 7 bit numbers representing strings of up to 21 zeroes followed by a 7 level residual sample. Our main concern with the use of this code was its susceptibility to transmission errors since the position of each sample is referenced to the previous sample. To eliminate this problem, we broke the frame into 10 segments so that the strings of zeroes are referenced to one of these segment boundaries, removing the dependence upon the position of the previous sample. This requires one additional bit per nonzero sample to signal whether to advance the sample reference boundary to the next frame segment. The additional bit must be error protected to avoid losing this positional information. With this scheme our bit rate allows 36 of the 210 residual samples to be quantized to values other than zero.

CENTER CLIPPING THRESHOLD

An important aspect of the center clipping quantizer is the clipping threshold. This threshold must be dynamically adjusted during quantization in such a way as to insure a fixed number of samples are quantized per frame.

We investigated methods of dynamically adjusting the threshold and arrived at an algorithm which uses the ideal center clipped residual signal, (see Figure 2c), generated without the quantizer in the loop as a model or template which the quantizer uses to adjust the center clipping threshold. The goal is to dynamically adjust the threshold to capture the 36 largest amplitude values of the quantized residual signal.

The algorithm found to most closely approach this goal is as follows: The initial value of the threshold, $T(1)$, is obtained from the ideal residual as:

$$T(1) = .4M + .6A$$

where M is the minimum nonzero ideal residual amplitude and A is the average of these amplitudes.

The threshold is then dynamically adjusted up or down according to whether the number of quantized residual samples is ahead or behind the number of nonzero samples in the ideal center clipped residual.

If the number of quantized samples is ahead of the ideal, the threshold is raised according to:

$$T(i) = T(1)[1 + .09(Q(i-1) - I(i-1))]^2$$

$$i = 1, 2, \dots, 210$$

where $Q(i)$ is the number of quantized samples thru sample i and $I(i)$ is the number of ideal nonzero residual samples thru sample i .

If the actual rate of residual quantization is behind the ideal we increase the rate of residual sample coding by lowering the clipping threshold according to:

$$T(i) = T(1)[1 - .09(I(i-1) - Q(i-1))]^2$$

Figure 2d is an example of this center clipping quantization.

SWITCHED SEGMENT QUANTIZATION

As mentioned earlier, we compare the S/R of the center clipping quantizer with a version of segmental quantization and then transmit whichever has the greater S/R. This version of segmental quantization is similar to that developed for 9600 bps. One bit alternating with two bits are used to code each residual sample for an average residual sample bit rate of 1.5. These alternating two and four levels are modified by a two bit segment multiplier which is updated five times per frame allowing the coded residual to more accurately follow energy changes during the frame. These segment multipliers and the residual frame energy are calculated from the ideal unquantized residual, (Figure 2c).

PITCH WHITENING

We gave considerable attention to optimizing the pitch whitening filter because it accomplishes the majority of the S/R energy reduction during voiced speech. To more closely track changing pitch, the filter parameters were updated at twice the frame rate. We observed that little improvement in residual energy reduction could be obtained by the use of a pitch predictor of higher than second order. This is because the extra taps perform primarily an interpolative function for average pitch values between those obtainable using a single tap. This interpolative function requires only two taps, the first being at the lag yielding the MMSE single tap S/R and the second being the adjacent lag having the greater autocorrelation. Compared to a third order pitch predictor, a second order predictor requires less bits for predictor coding, and stability is more easily guaranteed. The practice had been to use an empirically derived test for third order stability and to drop back to first order if an unstable frame was encountered. We observed that a sufficient condition for stability was that the sum of the tap weights not exceed unity. During high energy voiced intervals both coefficients of the second order filter are positive and their sum exceeds unity often enough to adversely affect S/Q if the loop is reduced to first order to maintain stability. By scaling the sum of the coefficients to be unity rather than dropping back to first order, stability is maintained without the disruption of changing order.

BIT ALLOCATION, QUANTIZATION AND CODING

Although we concentrated on algorithms to improve quantization of the error signal, we also wanted to ensure that the variance of the error signal was as small as possible. Given the constraint of a 16 Kbps data rate, we had to trade off frame rate, pitch accuracy, pitch predictor order and spectral predictor order. We observed that the spectrum predictor could be fixed for periods as long as 25 to 30 milliseconds with little degradation. The pitch predictor needed a faster frame rate. We decided to fix the basic frame period to 26.25 milliseconds but to transmit two sets of pitch predictors every frame. This frame rate provided 420 bits per frame and 210 speech samples per frame.

One of these 420 bits had to specify which of the two types of residual quantizers was to be used each frame. For the segment quantizer, we felt that 315 bits (1.5 bits per speech sample) was the most that could be afforded. We considered two types of quantizers that met this limit. The first coded a pair of samples as eight possible combinations of levels; three levels for each sample with one particular combination of levels prohibited. The second type coded even samples with two bits (4 levels) and odd samples with one bit (2 levels). Experimental results showed this second type to be superior. Additionally, coding pairs of samples has the undesirable property that a single bit error could effect two samples.

Since we allocated 1.5 bits per sample for the standard segment quantizer, a total of 103 bits per frame were left for all side information for that quantizer. This information included nine reflection coefficients, two pitch lags, two second order pitch predictors, frame and segment energy, error protection and a synchronization bit. The same side information was needed for the center clipping quantizer except for segment energy.

FRAME ENERGY QUANTIZATION

Information is sent each frame pertaining to the level of the error signal. The form of this information is different for the segmental quantizer and the center clipping quantizer. In the center clipping quantizer a parameter is computed based on the average magnitude of the 36 largest ideal error signal samples. For the segment quantizer the parameter is based on the RMS value of all of the ideal error samples. We found that five bits were adequate to quantize either of these parameters. Using a large sample of speech, a separate 32 level minimum MSE (Max) quantizer was calculated for each of these two parameters.

In previous work at 9.6 Kbps [2], we had discovered that providing energy information for subframes or segments of the residual provided improved performance for bit-by-bit quantization of the error signal. This technique was used for the segmental quantizer in this APC-HQ. We divided the frame into five segments and used two bits for each segment to define which of four multiplication factors of the frame energy should be applied. The multiplication factors, which ranged from about .4 to 1.5, were determined by MSE quantization.

REFLECTION COEFFICIENT QUANTIZATION

We based the bit allocation and quantization of the reflection coefficients (RC's) on optimum scalar quantization principles. First we created a file of RC's for a large sample of speech. After computing the variance of each RC, we computed a bit allocation based on:

$$b(i) = B + .5 \lg \left\{ \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n V(i)}{V(i)} \right\}^{1/n}$$

where B, the total number of bits allocated to the set, was chosen so that the mean square error caused by quantizing any RC was less than .1 dB. This resulted in B equal to 36 bits and, after rounding to integer values, a bit allocation of (5,5,4,4,4,4,4,3,3) for the nine RC's. We then used the file of RC's to compute the levels for a set of non-uniform minimum mean square error (Max) quantizers. Measurements of the SNR of the APC-HQ before and after RC quantization showed no loss in SNR.

PITCH PREDICTOR QUANTIZATION

We limited the pitch period for each half-frame to 20 to 147 samples (400 to 54.4 Hz) to allow 7 bit coding. Pitch changes slowly enough to allow differential coding of one half-frame pitch period. We chose the second half-frame for absolute coding and the first half-frame for differential coding because the second half frame more often possesses a good pitch correlation at voicing onset. We experimentally verified that 3-bit differential coding (-4 to +3 lags) of the first half-frame pitch relative to the second caused no measurable loss in SNR.

Our strategy for coding the two pitch gains for each half-frame was based on several observations: (1) the predictors were never negative when the speech was voiced; (2) the two predictors had identical probability density functions; (3) the predictors were correlated and this correlation was increased when their sum was scaled to unity from a sum greater than unity. When we calculated the long-term Karhunen Loeve Transform for the two predictors, the decorrelating rotation was 45 degrees.

The variance of the decorrelated parameters was sufficiently different to warrant quantizing the first with twice as many levels as the second. After some experimentation we chose respectively 4 bit and 3 bit MSE quantization. On a large sample of speech, this quantization of the pitch predictors caused a loss in SNR of only .05 dB.

ERROR CORRECTION

Previous experience with APC had taught us that the side information in APC was much more sensitive to channel errors than the residual information. Since our goal was to be able to use the coder at random error rates up to five percent, we needed to error protect the most important bits of the most important parameters. After the error signal and all parameters had been quantized, a total of 28 bits were available for protecting the side information. One of these bits was used to duplicate the quantizer type bit.

Both of these bits are heavily error protected, and should they disagree due to an uncorrectable transmission error, the receiver repeats the speech from the previous frame. We allocated the remaining 27 bits to the parity portion of two Golais (23,12) codes and one (21,16) shortened Hamming code. Since the Golais codes provide more error immunity than the (21,16) code, they were used to protect the most significant bit(s) of the parameters. The (21,16) code was used to provide less protection to some of the less important bits. The least important bits of most of the parameters were not protected at all.

To provide protection for the positional information bit for each of the 36 coded residual samples of the center clipping quantizer, we used three Golais (24,12) codes. This means that each residual sample requires a total of 9 bits, including 7 bits for relative position and amplitude, 1 bit to indicate whether or not to move forward one segment, and one bit (average) to error protect the segment movement bit. The receiver repeats the speech from the previous frame if an uncorrectable error is detected by any of these (24,12) codes.

RESULTS AND CONCLUSIONS

The APC-HQ system just described obtains an average segmental SNR of 17 dB. It is instructive to compare the qualitative difference between speech coded by APC-HQ and speech coded by segmental quantization alone. Segmental quantization, although only slightly lower in segmental SNR, still has a hissy background at 16 Kbps. Noise shaping was found to not improve the quality, perhaps because the quantization error of the 1.5 bit average quantizer was not white as required for effective noise shaping. The APC-HQ system effectively reduces this background distortion and the speech is cleaner and crisper sounding.

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FIGURE 1 - APC-HQ

Figure 2a - Input Speech

Figure 2b - Output Speech

Figure 2c - Ideal Residual Magnitudes

Figure 2d - Quantizer Input and Output

REFERENCES

1. Atal, Bishnu S., "Predictive Coding of Speech at Low Bit Rates", IEEE Transactions on Communications, pp. 600-614, April 1982.
2. Tremain, Thomas E., et al, "Implementation of Two Real Time Narrowband Speech Algorithms", EASTCON , pp. 698-708, September 1978.
3. Viswanathan, R., et al, "Noisy-Channel Performance of 16 KB/S APC Coders", ICASSP-81, pp. 615-618, March 1981.
4. Burgett, Jim, and Collura, John, "REAL TIME IMPLEMENTATION OF 16 KBPS APC WITH HYBRID QUANTIZATION", ICASSP-84, March 1984.